

Optical properties of a tunable microcavity/microsphere polymeric composite

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Abstract

The combination of a microcavity and a microsphere has been proposed in this work to manipulate light in terms of emission wavelength and propagation direction. A microcavity with a layer of molecular photoswitch between two one-dimensional photonic crystals of poly vinyl carbazole and cellulose acetate has been designed. To tune the microcavity, the molecular photoswitch has been excited taking into account its cyclization upon irradiation 313 nm and its cycloreversion at 450 nm. In this way, the emission peak of the microcavity switches from 508.5 nm to 525 nm. A polystyrene microsphere with a radius of 1 micrometer is placed near the microcavity. With the detector at an angle of 8 degrees, the emission at 525 nm is 1.73 times higher with respect to the emission at 508.5 nm, while at 10.8 degrees, the emission at 508.5 nm is 1.45 times higher with respect to the emission at 525 nm. The value of these findings is that they offer the experimentalists with a ready means to compare the optical data of these types of composites with theory.

Keywords: Polymeric microcavities; polymeric microspheres; light scattering; photochromic materials.

Introduction

Optical microcavities are very versatile structures that can be exploited to achieve laser emission or spontaneous emission enhancement [1–4]. The typical structure of a monolithic microcavity is a defect layer of a certain material surrounded by two one-dimensional photonic crystals, also called distributed Bragg reflectors. In general, a photonic crystal is a metamaterial with a modulation of the refractive index leads to an energy region, i.e., the photonic band gap, in which light is not allowed to pass through the crystal [5–7]. In an optical microcavity the judicious choice of materials and layer thickness lead to an emission peak (or peaks) within the photonic band gap. Optical microcavities can be tuned in terms of emission peak spectral position with different external stimuli, such as the electric field [8] or light [9]. An additional control to the propagation of light is offered by the light scattering of microspheres. The scattering of a plane electromagnetic wave by a dielectric sphere is rigorously described by the Mie theory [10,11]. Several efficient approximations of Mie theory have been proposed [12,13]. Remarkably, J. E. Gordon has developed a simple expression to approximate Mie scattering [13].

In this work the combination of a tunable polymeric microcavity and a microsphere has been proposed in order to control the emission wavelength with the microcavity and the direction of light after the scattering by the microsphere. The microcavity has been designed by placing a defect layer of the molecular photoswitch diarylethene1 [14] between two one-dimensional photonic crystals made by poly vinyl carbazole (PVK) and cellulose acetate (CA). The two polymers have been selected because of the high refractive index contrast [15]. Upon ultraviolet irradiation on the molecular photoswitch, the emission peak of the microcavity shifts from 508.5 nm to 525 nm. After the microcavity, the emitted light impinges the poly styrene microsphere and is scattered. A detector is

placed at certain angles and the emission intensity at the two wavelengths is altered via the microsphere scattering.

Methods

To simulate the photonic crystals, the microcavity, and the microsphere, different theoretical methods have been employed. To simulate the transmission spectrum of the two one-dimensional photonic crystals that constitute the microcavity, the expressions derived and analyzed by Brovelli and Keller [16] are used and compared with the transfer matrix method.

In the photonic crystal, the low refractive index layers have refractive index n_L and thickness d_L , while the high refractive index layers have refractive index n_H and thickness d_H . The reflection coefficient can be written as [16]

$$r = \exp\left[-i\frac{2\pi}{\Lambda}(z_1 - s)\right] \frac{-\kappa \sinh(\Gamma l)}{\Gamma \cosh(\Gamma l) - i\delta \sinh(\Gamma l)} \quad (1)$$

in which

$$\Lambda = d_L + d_H \quad (2)$$

$$\Gamma = \sqrt{\kappa^2 - \delta^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{2\Delta n}{\lambda} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta n = n_H + n_L \quad (5)$$

$$\delta = \beta - \pi/\Lambda \quad (6)$$

$$\beta = \bar{n}k \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{n} = \frac{n_H d_H + n_L d_L}{\Lambda} \quad (8)$$

$$k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \quad (9)$$

where λ is the wavelength, z_1 is the position of the beginning of the photonic crystal, while s is the position of the middle of the photonic crystal (i.e., $z_1 - s$ corresponds to half the thickness of the photonic crystal). The reflection is

$$R = |r|^2 \quad (10)$$

Brovelli and Keller have derived an expression that takes into account the substrate and the air on top of the photonic crystal [16]

$$t = \frac{2(-1)^{NB} \beta_1 \beta_2 \Gamma}{\Gamma C \beta_2 (\beta_3 + \beta_1) + \kappa \beta_2 S (\beta_3 - \beta_1 + 2i\kappa) + i\delta S [i\kappa(\beta_3 - \beta_1) - \beta_2^2 - \beta_1 \beta_3 - \kappa^2]} \quad (11)$$

Where $\beta_{1,2,3}$ is the parameter β of Equation 7 for the substrate, the photonic crystal, and air, respectively. NB is the number of bilayers of the photonic crystal. C and S are, respectively

$$C = \cosh(\Gamma NB \Lambda); \quad S = \sinh(\Gamma NB \Lambda) \quad (12)$$

The transmission is thus

$$T = \frac{n_0}{n_s} |t|^2 \quad (13)$$

n_s and n_0 are the refractive indexes of the substrate (glass, $n_s = 1.46$) and air ($n_0 \sim 1$), respectively. The transfer matrix method is a well-established theoretical tool employed to simulate the optical properties of stratified media [17–23]. The system studied is glass/stratified medium/air with light that impinges the sample orthogonally with respect to the sample surface (transmission spectra for TE and TM waves are the same in this configuration [24]). Within such method the parameter

$$\phi_k(\lambda) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} n_k(\lambda) d_k \quad (14)$$

is employed in the characteristic matrix for the k th layer [17]

$$M_k = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\phi_k(\lambda) & -\frac{i}{n_k(\lambda)} \sin\phi_k(\lambda) \\ -in_k(\lambda) \sin\phi_k(\lambda) & \cos\phi_k(\lambda) \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

with $n_k(\lambda)$ and d_k the refractive index and the thickness, respectively, of the k th layer. The matrix for the multilayer is given by

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} \\ M_{21} & M_{22} \end{bmatrix} = \prod_{i=1}^N M_k \quad (16)$$

With N the number of layers. From the matrix M it is possible to find out the transmission coefficient t

$$t = \frac{2n_s}{(M_{11} + M_{12}n_0)n_s + (M_{21} + M_{22}n_0)} \quad (17)$$

Then, the transmission can be derived using Equation 13.

For the microsphere scattering, the expression derived by Gordon has been used [13]. The relative scattering intensity is

$$I_\vartheta = I_0 \left[\frac{|3J_1(x)|}{x} - x^{-\frac{3}{2}} \right]^2 \frac{1 + \cos^2\vartheta}{2} \quad (18)$$

With J_1 first-order spherical Bessel function of the first kind

$$J_1(x) = \frac{\sin x - x \cos x}{x^2} \quad (19)$$

And x

$$x = ka\sqrt{1 + m^2 - 2m\cos\vartheta} \quad (20)$$

Where $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ (in which λ is the wavelength), a is the radius of the scattering particle, and m is the ratio of the refractive indexes of the scattering nanoparticle and the surrounding medium.

Results and Discussion

A sketch of the apparatus designed in this work is depicted in Figure 1. Light is impinging the microcavity surface orthogonally. Then, the light transmitted through the microcavity is scattered by the microsphere. A detector is placed at angle ϑ with respect to the axis orthogonal to the microcavity. As molecular photoswitch, the molecule diarylethene1 has been chosen [14]. For this molecule, cyclization occurs upon irradiation 313 nm and cycloreversion occurs upon irradiation at 450 nm.

Figure 1. Sketch of the apparatus. Light impinges the one-dimensional photonic crystal. The light transmitted through the photonic crystal impinges the nanoparticle. With respect to the direction perpendicular to the photonic crystal, the detector is placed after the microsphere at angle ϑ .

For the simulation of the photonic crystals and the microcavity, the dispersion of the refractive indexes of the materials constituting the multilayer structures have been taken into account. The Sellmeier equations have been used for this purpose [25,26]. The Sellmeier equation for the refractive index of PVK is given by [27,28]

$$n_{PVK}^2(\lambda) - 1 = \frac{0.09788\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.3257^2} + \frac{0.6901\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.1419^2} + \frac{0.8513\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 1.1417^2} \quad (21)$$

While the Sellmeier equation for the refractive index of CA is [27,28]

$$n_{CA}^2(\lambda) - 1 = \frac{0.6481\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.0365^2} + \frac{0.5224\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.1367^2} + \frac{2.483\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 13.54^2} \quad (22)$$

In the Sellmeier equations λ is in micrometers. The complex refractive index, as a function of wavelength, of diarylethene1, in its open and close form, has been taken from Ref. [29].

In Figure 2 the transmission spectrum of a one-dimensional photonic crystal made with 25 bilayers of PVK and CA is shown. The expressions by Brovelli and Keller, Equations 1 and 11 in this work (which correspond to Equation 8, BK8 in Figure 2, and Equation 16, BK16 in Figure 2, respectively, in Ref. [16]), have been used. For BK8 light transmission has been considered as $T = 1 - R$ because of the negligible absorption of the materials composing the photonic crystal in the studied range. The agreement with the transfer matrix method (black curve) is very good in the photonic band gap region.

Figure 2. Red curve: Light transmission of the PVK/CA photonic crystal following Equation 8 by Brovelli and Keller (BK8, Equation 1 in this work) [16]; blue curve: Light transmission of the PVK/CA photonic crystal following Equation 16 by Brovelli and Keller (BK16, Equation 11 in this work) [16]; black curve: Light transmission of the PVK/CA photonic crystal using the transfer method. For BK8 light transmission has been considered as $T = 1 - R$, since the absorption of the materials composing the photonic crystal has been neglected.

The microcavity is designed following the sequence $(\text{PVK}/\text{CA})_{25}/\text{diarylethene1}/(\text{PS}/\text{PVK})_{25}$, i.e., a defect layer of diarylethene1 placed between two one-dimensional photonic crystals made by 25 bilayers of PVK and CA. The thickness of the PVK and CA layers is 80 nm, while the thickness of the diarylethene1 defect layer is 170 nm. In Figure 3 the tuning of the microcavity via excitation of the molecular photoswitch diarylethene1 is shown. Upon irradiation at 313 nm, diarylethene1 switches from the open form to the closed form. Consequently, then transmission spectrum of the microcavity switches from the one depicted in Figure 3 with a solid black curve to the one depicted with a dashed red curve. The defect of the microcavity leads to an emission peak with the photonic band gap region. Such emission peak is at 508.5 nm for diarylethene1 in its open form, and at 525 nm for diarylethene1 in its closed form.

Figure 3. Transmission spectra for a microcavity (PVK/CA)₂₅/diarylethene1/(PS/PVK)₂₅ in its open (solid black curve) and closed form (dashed red curve).

The radius of the poly styrene microsphere of Figure 1 is 1 micrometer and the surrounding medium is air, with refractive index $n_0 \sim 1$. The dispersion of the refractive index of poly styrene is [30,31]

$$n_{PS}^2(\lambda) - 1 = \frac{1.4435\lambda^2}{\lambda^2 - 0.020216^2} \quad (23)$$

A constant value is used in this work, since, according to Equation 23, the refractive index at 508.5 nm is 1.6019, while the refractive index at 525 nm is 1.5993. Thus, the value of the refractive index of the polystyrene microsphere, employed in this work, is 1.6. In Figure 4 the relative scattering intensity is displayed as a function of the detection angle (ϑ in Figure 1) and the wavelength.

Figure 4. Contour plot of the relative scattering intensity as a function of the angle (ϑ in Figure 1) and as a function of the wavelength.

In Figure 5 the relative scattering intensity is depicted for the emission peak of the microcavity, at 508.5 nm (blue curve) for the open form of diarylethene1 and at 525 nm (red curve) for the closed form of diarylethene1.

Figure 5. Relative scattering intensity as a function of the angle at 508.5 nm and at 525 nm.

It is remarkable that, with the detector at an angle of 8 degrees (ϑ in Figure 1), the emission at 525 nm is 1.73 times higher with respect to the emission at 508.5 nm, while at 10.8 degrees, the emission at 508.5 nm is 1.45 times higher with respect to the emission at 525 nm.

Conclusion

The synergy of a polymer microcavity and a microsphere was exploited to control the emission wavelength with the tunable microcavity and the direction of light after scattering by the microsphere. The microcavity was designed by placing a layer of diarylethene1 molecular photoswitch defects between two one-dimensional photonic crystals consisting of poly vinyl carbazole (PVK) and cellulose acetate (CA). Upon ultraviolet irradiation of the molecular photoswitch, the microcavity emission peak shifts from 508.5 nm to 525 nm. After the microcavity, the emitted light hits the poly-styrene microsphere and is scattered. A detector is placed at certain angles, and the intensity of the emission at the two wavelengths is altered by the scattering of the microsphere. These results can be useful for light manipulation and optical device-based sensing.

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References

- [1] J. Faist, J. -D. Ganière, Ph. Buffat, S. Sampson, F. -K. Reinhart, Characterization of GaAs/(GaAs)_n(AlAs)_m surface-emitting laser structures through reflectivity and high-resolution

- electron microscopy measurements, *Journal of Applied Physics*. 66 (1989) 1023–1032. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.343488>.
- [2] W. Hsin, G. Du, J.K. Gamelin, K.J. Malloy, S. Wang, J.R. Whinnery, Y.J. Yang, T.G. Dziura, S.C. Wang, Low threshold distributed Bragg reflector surface emitting laser diode with semiconductor air-bridge-supported top mirror, *Electron. Lett.* 26 (1990) 307. <https://doi.org/10.1049/el:19900202>.
- [3] K.J. Vahala, Optical microcavities, *Nature*. 424 (2003) 839–846. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature01939>.
- [4] H. Takeuchi, K. Natsume, S. Suzuki, H. Sakata, Microcavity distributed-feedback laser using dye-doped polymeric thin films, *Electronics Letters*. 43 (2007) 30–31. <https://doi.org/10.1049/el:20073399>.
- [5] S. John, Strong localization of photons in certain disordered dielectric superlattices, *Physical Review Letters*. 58 (1987) 2486–2489. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.58.2486>.
- [6] E. Yablonovitch, Inhibited Spontaneous Emission in Solid-State Physics and Electronics, *Physical Review Letters*. 58 (1987) 2059–2062. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.58.2059>.
- [7] J.D. Joannopoulos, ed., *Photonic crystals: molding the flow of light*, 2nd ed, Princeton University Press, Princeton, 2008.
- [8] L. Xiao, Y. Lv, J. Lin, Y. Hu, W. Dong, X. Guo, Y. Fan, N. Zhang, J. Zhao, Y. Wang, X. Liu, WO₃-Based Electrochromic Distributed Bragg Reflector: Toward Electrically Tunable Microcavity Luminescent Device, *Advanced Optical Materials*. 6 (2018) 1700791. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adom.201700791>.
- [9] F. Scotognella, Tunable cavity modes in diarylethene-based photo-switchable polymeric microcavities and study of the light-pulse propagation through the microcavities, *Results in Optics*. 10 (2023) 100338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rio.2022.100338>.
- [10] G. Mie, Beiträge zur Optik trüber Medien, speziell kolloidaler Metallösungen, *Annalen Der Physik*. 330 (1908) 377–445. <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19083300302>.
- [11] C.F. Bohren, D.R. Huffman, *Absorption and Scattering of Light by Small Particles*, 1st ed., Wiley, 1998. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527618156>.
- [12] K. Shimizu, Modification of the Rayleigh–Debye approximation, *J. Opt. Soc. Am., JOS A*. 73 (1983) 504–507. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSA.73.000504>.
- [13] J.E. Gordon, Simple method for approximating Mie scattering, *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A, JOSAA*. 2 (1985) 156–159. <https://doi.org/10.1364/JOSAA.2.000156>.
- [14] M. Morimoto, T. Sumi, M. Irie, Photoswitchable Fluorescent Diarylethene Derivatives with Thiophene 1,1-Dioxide Groups: Effect of Alkyl Substituents at the Reactive Carbons, *Materials*. 10 (2017) 1021. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma10091021>.
- [15] T. Komikado, S. Yoshida, S. Umegaki, Surface-emitting distributed-feedback dye laser of a polymeric multilayer fabricated by spin coating, *Applied Physics Letters*. 89 (2006) 061123. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2336740>.
- [16] L.R. Brovelli, U. Keller, Simple analytical expressions for the reflectivity and the penetration depth of a Bragg mirror between arbitrary media, *Optics Communications*. 116 (1995) 343–350. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-4018\(95\)00084-L](https://doi.org/10.1016/0030-4018(95)00084-L).
- [17] M. Born, E. Wolf, A.B. Bhatia, P.C. Clemmow, D. Gabor, A.R. Stokes, A.M. Taylor, P.A. Wayman, W.L. Wilcock, *Principles of Optics: Electromagnetic Theory of Propagation, Interference and Diffraction of Light*, 7th ed., Cambridge University Press, 1999. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139644181>.
- [18] Y.G. Boucher, A. Chiasera, M. Ferrari, G.C. Righini, Extended transfer matrix modeling of an erbium-doped cavity with SiO₂/TiO₂ Bragg reflectors, *Optical Materials*. 31 (2009) 1306–1309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2008.10.028>.

- [19] X. Xiao, W. Wenjun, L. Shuhong, Z. Wanquan, Z. Dong, D. Qianqian, G. Xuexi, Z. Bingyuan, Investigation of defect modes with Al₂O₃ and TiO₂ in one-dimensional photonic crystals, *Optik*. 127 (2016) 135–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijleo.2015.10.005>.
- [20] A.H. Aly, S.-W. Ryu, H.-T. Hsu, C.-J. Wu, THz transmittance in one-dimensional superconducting nanomaterial-dielectric superlattice, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*. 113 (2009) 382–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2008.07.123>.
- [21] A.M. Ahmed, A. Mehaney, Novel design of wide temperature ranges sensor based on Tamm state in a pyroelectric photonic crystal with high sensitivity, *Physica E: Low-Dimensional Systems and Nanostructures*. 125 (2021) 114387. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2020.114387>.
- [22] J. Wu, J. Gao, Multi-band absorption characteristics of a metal-loaded graphene-based photonic crystal, *Physica E: Low-Dimensional Systems and Nanostructures*. 129 (2021) 114675. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2021.114675>.
- [23] A.H. Aly, D. Mohamed, M.A. Mohaseb, Metamaterial Control of Hybrid Multifunctional High-Tc Superconducting Photonic Crystals for 1D Quasi-periodic Structure Potential Applications, *Mat. Res.* 23 (2020) e20190695. <https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-5373-mr-2019-0695>.
- [24] M. Bellingeri, A. Chiasera, I. Kriegel, F. Scotognella, Optical properties of periodic, quasi-periodic, and disordered one-dimensional photonic structures, *Optical Materials*. 72 (2017) 403–421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.optmat.2017.06.033>.
- [25] A. Natesan, K.P. Govindasamy, T.R. Gopal, V. Dhasarathan, A.H. Aly, Tricore photonic crystal fibre based refractive index sensor for glucose detection, *IET Optoelectronics*. 13 (2019) 118–123. <https://doi.org/10.1049/iet-opt.2018.5079>.
- [26] I.S. Amiri, B.K. Paul, K. Ahmed, A.H. Aly, R. Zakaria, P. Yupapin, D. Vigneswaran, Tri-core photonic crystal fiber based refractive index dual sensor for salinity and temperature detection, *Microwave and Optical Technology Letters*. 61 (2019) 847–852. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mop.31612>.
- [27] L. Fornasari, F. Floris, M. Patrini, D. Comoretto, F. Marabelli, Demonstration of fluorescence enhancement via Bloch surface waves in all-polymer multilayer structures, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* 18 (2016) 14086–14093. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5CP07660A>.
- [28] G. Manfredi, C. Mayrhofer, G. Kothleitner, R. Schennach, D. Comoretto, Cellulose ternary photonic crystal created by solution processing, *Cellulose*. 23 (2016) 2853–2862. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-016-1031-x>.
- [29] F. Scotognella, Multilayer plasmonic photonic structures embedding photochromic molecules or optical gain molecules, *Physica E: Low-Dimensional Systems and Nanostructures*. (2020) 114081. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physe.2020.114081>.
- [30] RefractiveIndex.INFO - Refractive index database, (n.d.). <https://refractiveindex.info/> (accessed November 15, 2019).
- [31] N. Sultanova, S. Kasarova, I. Nikolov, Dispersion Properties of Optical Polymers, *Acta Physica Polonica A*. 116 (2009) 585–587. <https://doi.org/10.12693/APhysPolA.116.585>.